



AUC result of the distribution model created for six *Sphagnum* species. The area under the curve (AUC), which is the area under the receiver-operating characteristic (ROC), was used to evaluate the accuracy of the model. The AUC values range from 0.5 to 1, with higher values indicating the better performance of the model: poor (0.5–0.6), fair (0.6–0.7), good (0.7–0.8), very good (0.8–0.9), and excellent (0.9–1.0).